

**SEYSMIK HIMOYA QILINGAN BINO VA INSHOOTLARNI TAHLIL
QILISH VA O'TGAN ZILZILALAR AKSELEROGRAMMASI****Buriyev A.T.**

F.-m.f.d., dots.

Abubakirova X.Y.

magistr.

(Toshkent arxitektura qurilish universiteti)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13747349>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada hozirgi kungacha Respublikamizda binolarni zilzilabardoshligi bo'yicha qo'llanilgan me'yoriy hujjatlar va ularning ahamiyati bo'yicha ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Oldin bo'lib o'tgan zilzilalar tahlili hamda akselerogrammalari keltirilgan. Hozirgi kunda loyihalananayotgan bino va inshootlar uchun tavsiyalar berilgan.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены нормативные акты, действовавшие на сегодняшний день в нашей республике по сейсмостойкости зданий, и информация об их значении. Приведен анализ предыдущих землетрясений, а также их акселерограммы. В настоящее время даны рекомендации по проектируемым зданиям и сооружениям.

Annotation. This article provides information on regulatory documents and their significance, which have been used to this day in our Republic on the earthquake activity of buildings. Analysis of previous earthquakes as well as accelerograms are presented. Recommendations have been made for buildings and structures currently being designed.

Kalit so'zlar. Zilzila, akselerogramma, bino va inshootlar, dinamik, davrlar, chastotalar, seysmik himoya qurilmalari.

Ключевые слова. Землетрясения, акселерограммы, здания и сооружения, динамические, схемы, частоты, устройства сейсмической защиты.

Keywords. Earthquake, accelerogram, buildings and structures, dynamics, periods, frequencies, seismic protection devices.

Kirish qism: Zilzilalar sodir bo'lishining asosiy qonuniyatlarini o'rganish bilan seysmologiya deb nomlangan fan shug'ullanadi. Ushbu fanning turli masalalari orasida Yerning tuzilishini o'rganish, zilzilalarning sabablari va sharoitlarini aniqlash, shuningdek zilzilalarning bino va inshootlarga ta'sirining tabiati va darajasini baholash, ularning zilzilaga chidamliligini ta'minlash choralarini ishlab chiqish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Yuqori intensivlikdagi zilzilalar ko'plab qurbonlar va vayronagarchiliklarga olib keladi. Dinamik

nazariyaga asoslangan dastlabki me'yoriy hujjat (SN-8-57) 1957 yilda qabul qilingandan keyin, chorak asr mobaynida fanning bu sohasida ulkan ilmiy tadqiqotlar amalga oshirildi; qator zilzilalar sodir bo'ldi. Zilzilalar bino loyihasi va qurilishida yo'l qo'yilgan xato va kamchiliklarni ro'y rost ko'rsatib berdi. Bularning hammasi qurilish me'yorlariga tegishli o'zgartirishlar, tuzatishlar kiritishga sabab bo'ldi. 1962 yili qabul qilingan SNIP II-A 12-62 to 1970 yilga qadar qo'llanishda bo'ldi. 1970 yil iyuldan 1981 yilning 31 dekabrigacha SNIP II -A 12-69 amal qilib keldi. 1982 yilning 1 yanvaridan boshlab, yangi me'yoriy hujjat SNIP II-7 -81 qo'llanila boshlandi. Ushbu me'yoriy hujjat O'zbekistonda 1996 yilga qadar qo'llanishda bo'ldi. 1996 yilning 1 martidan e'tiboran O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududida yangi qurilish me'yorlari va qoidalari (QMQ 2.01.03- 96) kuchga kirdi. Ushbu rasmiy hujjatning joriy etilishi munosabati bilan SNIP II -7-81 ning 1,2,3 qismlari va 1,2 ilovalari o'z kuchini yo'qotdi. SHNK 2.01.03-19 "Seysmik hududlarda qurilish" me'yoriy hujjatning 5 betida zilzilalarning spektrial vaqt xususiyatlariga qarab seysmik kuchning eng past qiymatlarini ta'minlaydigan konstruktiv sxemalarini qo'llash tavsiya etilgan.

Asosiy qism: Zilzilaga moyil bo'lgan ma'lum bir hududning mahalliy sharoitlarini, shu jumladan tuproqlarning fizik dinamik xususiyatlarini, yer qobig'ining yuqori qatlamlarining kuchini, relefnig xususiyatlarini va seysmik to'lqinlarning spektral tarkibi, seysmik xaritalarni tahlil qilishni hisobga olgan holda ushbu ma'lumotlarni umumlashtirish asosida. rayonlashtirish bilan tuzilgan va o'rtacha zamin sharoitida geografik aholi punktlari uchun seysmik ko'lamli punktlarida zilzilalar intensivligini ko'rsatiladi. Akselerogrammalarni tanlashda adabiyotda mavjud bo'lgan o'tmishdagi zilzilalar yozuvlaridan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Misol tariqasida quyidagi zilzilalar tahlili 1-jadvalda keltirilgan.

O'tgan zilzilalarning ishlatilgan akselerogrammalarining xususiyatlari

1-jadval

Zilzila bo'lgan hudud	Ballar soni	Raqamlashtirish bosqichi	Davomiyligi	Davrlar	Indeksi
Helena (Kaliforniya)	216	0.03	6.45	0.25	0.379
Toshkent	286	0.0091	2.59	0.12	0.364
Vernoon (Kaliforniya)	400	0.02	7.98	0.23	0.261
Gazli	1990	0.005	13.07	0.15	0.272

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

1-ram. Gazlida bo'lgan zilzila akselerogrammasi.

2-ram. Vernoonda bo'lgan zilzila akselerogrammasi.

3-ram. Helenada bo'lgan zilzila akselerogrammasi.

Hozirgi vaqtda zilzila akselerogrammalari bo'yicha bino va inshootlarni hisoblashda seysmik ta'sirni tayinlash bo'yicha universal tavsiyalar mavjud emas. Mavjud tadqiqotlar hisob-kitoblarni amalga oshirish uchun o'tmishdagi zilzilalarning akselerogrammalaridan va turli xil sintetik akselerogrammalardan foydalaniladi. Ko'rib chiqilgan zilzilalar eng kuchli hisoblanadi. Hozirgi kunda ushbu zilzila tahlillaridan foydalanish orqali bino va inshootlarni hisoblash mumkin.

Xulosa. Bino va inshootlarni seysmik holatini o'rganish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, loyiha jarayonida hududda bo'lib o'tgan zilzilalar tahlilidan foydalanib binolarni loyihalash binolarni zilzila vaqtida mustahkamligini ta'minlaydi. Seysmiklik uchun 8 balldan ortiq hududlarda seymik himoya qurilmalaridan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

References:

1. Machmudov S. M., Samieva S. K. Quantitative assessment of the reliability of the system" foundation-seismic isolation foundation-building" //Central Asian Journal of STEM. – 2021. – T.– №. 2. – С. 445-452. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=kzGnBtQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=kzGnBtQAAAAJ:9yKSN-GCBOIC
2. Махмудов С. М., Самиева Ш. Х. КОНСТРУКТИВНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ СЕЙСМОИЗОЛИРУЮЩИХ ФУНДАМЕНТОВ ЗДАНИЙ //НАУЧНЫЕ

РЕВОЛЮЦИИ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ФАКТОР РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ И ТЕХНИКИ. – 2021. – С. 36-38. <https://os-russia.com/SBORNIKI/KON-393.pdf#page=36>

3. Khushvaqtovna S. S. Prof. Makhmudov Said Makhmudovich //Study of the Operation of a Building Model with a Seismic Isolation Sliding Belt//INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS ISSN (print). – С. 2643-9840.

<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=11592764159241392371&hl=en&oi=scholar>

4. Maxmudov S. M., Samiyeva S. X., Ruziyev S. I. ZILZILA PAYTIDA BINONING ZAMIN BILAN O'ZARO TA'SIRINI VA SEYSMIK TA'SIRNING O'ZGARISHINI HISOBGA OLISH //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 151-153. <https://researchedu.org/index.php/goldenbrain/article/view/4325>

5. Makhmudov S. M., Samiyeva S. X., Roziev S. I. MODELING OF SEISMIC PROTECTION USING VISCOUS AND DRY FRICTION DAMPERS //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 70-73.

<https://researchedu.org/index.php/goldenbrain/article/view/4304>

6. Самиева Ш., Махмудов С. Экспериментальные исследования сейсмостойкости зданий //Сейсмическая безопасность зданий и сооружений. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 271-274.

<https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/seismic-safety-buildings/article/view/27518>

7. GMFN, Dos, Samiyeva Sh Kh, and Master MA Muminov. "DEFORMATION OF MOISTENED LOESS FOUNDATIONS OF BUILDINGS UNDER STATIC AND DYNAMIC LOADS." (2022).

<https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejrds/article/view/3049>

8. Khakimov G. A. et al. COMPACTION OF LOESS BASES OF BUILDINGS AND STRUCTURES, AS WELL AS BULK SOILS AROUND THE FOUNDATION USING VIBRATORY ROLLERS IN SEISMIC AREAS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 4. – С. 306-311.

<https://www.giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/5184>

9. Махмудов С. и др. Special sliding belt supports that protect buildings and structures from earthquakes //Сейсмическая безопасность зданий и сооружений. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 90-94.

<https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/seismic-safety-buildings/article/view/27570>

10. Khushvaqtovna S. S., Makhmudovich M. S. SEISMIC REACTION OF FRAME BUILDINGS WITH A COMBINED SEISMIC PROTECTION SYSTEM //IMRAS. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 151-157.

11. <https://journal.imras.org/index.php/sps/article/view/1080>

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

12. Бердимуродов, А., & Собирова, З. (2023). Zilzilaga chidamli binolarning konstruktiv elementlari. Сейсмическая безопасность зданий и сооружений, 1(1), 185–189. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/seismic-safety-buildings/article/view/27589>
13. Eshnazarovich, B. A. (2024). ZILZILAVIY HUDUDLARDA LYOSSLI ZAMINNI ZICHLASH USULLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 42(2), 13-20. <https://newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/13038>
14. Eshnazarovich, B. A. (2024). STRUCTURE SOLUTIONS FOR THE CONSTRUCTION AND REPAIR OF FOUNDATIONS ON LOESS SOILS IN SEISMIC ZONES. Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement, 1(7), 56–61. <https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i7.732>
15. Eshnazarovich, B. A. ., & Abduxalilovich, M. A. . (2024). ZILZILA KUCHI TA'SIRIGA BARDOSH BERADIGAN BINOLARNING KONSTRUKTIV YECHIMLARI. ARHITEKTURA, MUHANDISLIK VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR JURNALI, 3(3), 11–16. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/arxitektura/ article/view/10037>

